

Correcting the dose calibration error in the pre-treatment verification of VMAT radiotherapy plans

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Abstract Purpose: To correct the dose calibration error in the pre-treatment verification of VMAT radiotherapy performed with the Octavius phantom and 729 detector array,

Methods: The gamma index measures the difference between the computed dose distribution by the treatment planning system and the dose distribution obtained with the QA device in pre-treatment plan verification. The gamma index is affected by several factors. One of these is the rotating phantom setup position error. In our previous study, we analyzed the influence of the rotating phantom's shift and we proposed a method to reduce it.

In the present study, we analyzed the factors concerning the dose delivery and the dose measurement of the QA plans affecting the gamma index and gamma distribution.

18 treatment plans of 16 prostate, bladder and rectum cancer patients' RT plans' Gamma distributions and Gamma index histograms were reviewed repeating the gamma analysis after rescaling the measured dose distributions by the factors between 0,99-1.03.

Results 4 patients' plans showed optimal Gamma histogram without rescaling, while 4-4 patients' plans showed better Gamma index distributions and Gamma index histograms after rescaling the measured QA plan's dose distributions with factors 1.01 or 1.02.

keywords: pre-treatment verification, rotating phantom

Introduction

At our institution, the pre-treatment verification of volumetric modulated arc (VMAT) radiotherapy plans (RTP) with the Octavius 4D phantom with 729 ion chamber array (PTW, GMBH, Freiburg, Germany) is performed. The verification of RTPs with the Verisoft program v6.2 (PTW) is based on the comparison of two 3D dose distributions. The first one is obtained from the measured 2D dose matrices by the ion chamber array, while the second one is the dose matrix of the corresponding RT plan adapted for the geometry of the Octavius phantom by the Monaco v5.11 treatment planning system (TPS) (Elekta BV., Sweden). The comparison of the two dose matrices for

spatial and dose differences is performed with gamma analysis. For definition and interpretation of the gamma index and gamma analysis see ref. [1]. The gamma index is affected by several factors analyzed by Urso et al.[2]. One of the factors is the phantom setup error. The Verisoft program offers the 'Align Automatically' function to correct the rotating phantom's setup error. This function works fine for simple dose distributions but often resulted in a poorer gamma index for complex dose distributions. In our previous study, we analyzed the influence of the rotating phantom [3].

In the present study, we analyzed the factors concerning the dose delivery and the dose measurement of the QA plans affecting the gamma index and gamma index distribution. We refer to them as dose calibration error.

At our institution, for the dose calibration of the Synergy clinac (Elekta, Sweden) the secondary standard dose meter Unidos and 3013 ion chamber (PTV Freiburg, Germany) is used. The dose measurement accuracy is 1% stated by the Calibration Bureau Budapest, Hungary. The clinac's dose rate calibration performed with the Unidos was checked with the IAEA/WHO postal TL quality assurance audit. The ion chamber based and the thermoluminescent (PTLD) capsule based dose measurement agreed within 1%. The dose delivery of the QA plans and the cross-calibration of the 729 detector array are affected by the daily and the temporary variation in dose rate of the clinac. We also reviewed the daily central axis dose values in the clinac's QA files performed with Quickcheck (PTW) and we found less than 1% variation.

The readings of the ionization chambers are affected by the received pre-irradiation dose [4] which is different for each ion chamber in the detector array. We investigated the Octavius system's consistency by periodically delivering 1Gy dose to the detector array during a QA measurement session, with fields of 0 gantry angle, 10x10cm field size. The variation of the dose measured by the central ion chamber as a function of time from the cross calibration is illustrated in Fig.1. We experienced a dose variation less than 0.2%.

Despite the good clinac and instrumentation stability and accurate dose calibration, the superposition of the dose-related uncertainties is not known exactly. Its value, estimated at 2%, is large compared to the 2% or 3% dose agreement criteria in the Gamma index computation.

The aim of the study is to decrease the influence of such factors in the Gamma index evaluation.

Fig.1. Variation of the dose measured by the ionchamber being at the center of the 729 detector array for 1Gy dose as a function of time (minutes) during a QA session.

Materials and methods

At our institution, before the pre-treatment verification session, the phantom is carefully positioned and leveled with the room lasers and the chamber array is cross-calibrated. To determine the rotating phantom's setup position error in the submillimeter range, we applied our method. We performed correction if the shift was larger than 0,5mm. Then We carried out the pre-treatment measurement of the RT plan and we computed the 3D dose distribution by the Verisoft program. After rescaling the measured dose distributions by the factors: 0.99, 1.01, 1.02 and 1.03, we repeated the gamma analysis calculation. In the gamma analysis, we used the restricted 2mm distance and 2% dose criteria. We also obtained the dose ratio of the measured and computed doses at the isocenter and the ratio of them (d_{meas} and d_{comp} , and the $ratio$ of them in Table 1. We analyzed the failed points' map and the Gamma index histograms too. 'n' and 'P' indicate cold and warm failed spots in the Gamma distributions, see Fig.4. We choosed the optimal rescale factor corresponding to the best Gamma index distribution indicated with '*' while the relative best one is indicated with 'o' in Table 1.

18 QA plans of 12 prostate, bladder and rectum cancer patients were evaluated. Among them, there were composite plans of 46 Gy to the pelvis as base plan, and sequential boosts to the medium and high risk PTVs. The RTPs were generated with the Monaco v5.11 treatment planning system with 6MV energy and the Monte Carlo algorithm. The

pre-treatment verification measurements were carried out with the Synergy linear accelerator with Agility MLC (Elekta B.V.)

session	patient	factor	0,99	1,00	1,01	1,02	1,03	dmeas	dcomp	ratio	* factor	gamma incr
1	1	1 boost	81,8 n	84,8 n	88,4 n	91,4 *	93,6 P	2,156	2,184	0,987	1,02	6,6
		1 base plan	73,1 n	77,7 n	81,4 *	84,0 *p	85,5 P	2,19	2,256	0,97	1,01	3,7
1	2		75,7 n	80,8 n	84,8 0	86,8 P	86,9 P	1,697	1,717	0,988	1,01	4
1	3		81,1 n	84,7 n	87,8 n	90,3 o	92,0 P	1,555	1,556	1	1,02	5,6
1	4		78,5 n	83,1 n	86,8 *	89,3 P	90,4 P	2,457	2,459	0,995	1,01	3,7
2	5	boost2	88,2 n	89,7 n	90,6 *	91,0 P	90,9 P	1,846	1,85	0,997	1,01	0,9
		boost1	90,6 n	92,3 n	93,5 *	94,2 P	94,2 P	1,951	2,009	0,97	1,01	1,2
		base plan	85,2 n	88,2 n	90,0 *	90,4 P	89,5 P	1,491	1,545	0,965	1,01	1,8
3	6		94,8 n	96,6 *	97,0 *P	98,0 P		1,575	1,552	1,01	1	0,4
4	7	boost2	94,8 n	96,8 n	97,8 *	98,5 P	98,5 P	2,037	2,038	1	1,01	1
		boost1	88,3 n	89,1 *	89,7 P	90,3 P	90,7 P	2,172	2,153	1,008	1	0,6
		base plan	82,4 n	85 *	86,4 P	86,8 P	86,0 P	2,013	1,966	1,02	1	1,4
5	8		81,3 n	85,9 *	88,6 P	89,4 P	88,3 P	1,706	1,773	0,96	1	0
5	9		78,2 n	81,5 n	84,7 n	86,9 *	88,5 P	1,587	1,616	0,98	1,02	5,4
5	10		73,6 n	77 n	79,9 0	82,1 *	83,5 P	2,281	2,329	0,98	1,02	5,1
6	11	base plan	78,8 n	82,6 n	85,4 n	87,1 *	87,5 P	1,459	1,49	0,98	1,02	4
		boost	91,6 n	93,8 n	95,3 n	95,2 *	96,5 P	1,608	1,687	0,95	1,02	4,5
6	12		91,9 n	93,5 *	94,1 P	93,8 P		1,356	1,355	1	1	0

Table 1. The Gamma indexes are shown after rescaling the measured dose distribution with the factors between 0,99 and 1.03

Fig.2. Typical variation of the Gamma index as a function of the rescale factor in the base plan (yellow), and in two boost plans of patient #7

Fig. 3 The optimal rescale factors as a function of the ratio of d_{meas} and d_{comp}

Fig.4. The suboptimal and optimal Gamma histograms, the latter is indicated by * in Table 1.

Fig 5. The variation of the Gamma indexes after rescaling the measured dose distribution with the optimal factor

Results

4 of the 12 patients' plans showed optimal Gamma distribution and Gamma index histograms without rescaling. After rescaling the other measured QA dose distributions with factors 1.01 or 1.02, 4-4 patients' plans showed better Gamma index histograms and higher Gamma indexes of up to 6.6%. In some cases, two neighboring rescale factors also resulted in an optimal Gamma histogram. We have found, that despite the given higher Gamma index values obtained with over the optimal rescale factors, they showed a poorer Gamma index histogram. We found medium correlation (-0.48) between the ratio of *dmeas* and *dcomp* and the optimal rescale factor.

Conclusion

By rescaling the measured dosed distributions with the factors 1.01 or 1.02, we was able to decrease the dose delivery and dose measurements errors. We found, that the Gamma index alone was not sufficient to indicate the match of the measured and computed QA dose distributions, the analysis of the Gamma index histograms and the failed points' map was also necessary.

Declaration of interest none.

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